

EFFECTIVE TECHNIQUES OF TEACHING VOCABULARY TO YOUNG LEARNERS.

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Abstract The article will discuss some effective ways of teaching vocabulary to young learners. Vocabulary is considered as the most essential part of a particular language. It is important to get acquainted with new words while learning languages. For this reason, some ways and techniques are recommended below which can be useful in teaching and learning process of vocabulary for the young generation.

Keywords: vocabulary, young learners, learning, teaching, language, teacher, communication, words, techniques.

Introduction

Children need to have a rich vocabulary that continually grows through language and literacy experiences, in order to comprehend and construct increasingly complex texts, and engage in oral language for a variety of social purposes. It's hard for students to read and understand a text if they don't know what the words mean. A solid vocabulary boosts reading comprehension for students of all ages. The more words students know, the better they understand the text. That's why effective vocabulary teaching is so important, especially for students who learn and think differently.

Main part

To improve and enrich our vocabularies there are some ways, for example by vocabulary. Name animal, media picture to get many words. Teachers have the important role to build children's vocabularies. They should know the factors in teaching such as methods, strategies, techniques, and materials, so that the teacher can convey the materials well in accordance with children's characteristics.

Learning vocabulary is a continual process of language and literacy development, which begins in the early years of life, and continues through schooling and beyond. Sinatra, Zygouris-Coe, and Dasinger note that:

Knowledge of vocabulary meanings affects children's abilities to understand and use words appropriately during the language acts of listening, speaking, reading, and writing. Such knowledge influences the complexities and nuances of children's thinking, how they communicate in the oral and written languages, and how well they will understand printed texts [1.333].

Young learners mean children from the first year of formal schooling (5 or 6 year old) to eleven or twelve year age. Young learners have own special characteristic that differentiate them from adult learners. It should be know and understood by the teacher to give contribution to improve their quality of teaching process (Halliwel, 1992). [3]

Techniques of Teaching Vocabulary:

There are three main stages in teaching vocabulary. In other word, there is some common techniques used in each stage as follow:

Techniques in Presenting. Yet it is the important stage that the student is introduced with the new words. As an English teacher, we should know the techniques of teaching vocabulary which are suitable for the students.

Techniques in Practicing. In practicing stage, there are a variety of tasks which can be used in order to help move words into long-term memory.

Media is a main instrument in teaching and learning process. It is used to attract the students' attention and deliver the information easily. Teachers of young learners have to use some visuals in their teaching activities to facilitate their teaching. According to Wright, there are various kinds of media, but visual is appropriate media for young learners in learning vocabulary.

Listen and Repeat technique was used by the teacher to introduce new vocabulary. In this technique the teacher asked the students to repeat after the words she read. The words were read slowly and repeatedly, so the students could follow

well. It was done continually and it made the students familiar with the new words [4].

In order to help young learners learn vocabulary effectively, we need to employ a range of strategies. First, we need to think why the young learner wants to know the words we teach as they are much more likely to remember them if they need them or want to use them. One way a teacher can do this is to get the learners to draw or write the words they already know and then draw or write the L1 translation of words they want to know. This can be followed by a spot of peer teaching where learners who know the second set of words teach them to the learners who want to know them. Another way to help young learners learn new words is to explore ways of recording vocabulary. Show learners some examples of picture dictionaries, words with sentences in English explaining what they mean and mind maps linking words and ideas. Discuss why these strategies are helpful. Encourage the learners to use these strategies when noting down new words.

It is crucial that children have explicit and robust instruction in vocabulary, to support their verbal and written communication. The explicit teaching of vocabulary allows students to access academic language and discourse, and facilitates their comprehension of increasingly complex texts [2].

Conclusion

If we want our young learners to be effective learners of vocabulary, we have to invest in teaching them strategies that help them to remember the words and produce them when they need them. Using the strategies above will help them develop their vocabulary and increase the total number of words they know.

List of used literature:

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